

Additional information about the interview participants

#	Role (anonymized)	Industry	No. of employees (worldwide)
1	Head of IT & Digital	Insurance	5,000 – 9,999
2	Head of corporate IT	Manufacturing	
3	Project manager (formerly executive assistant)	Software development	
4	Enterprise architect	Retail	≥ 10,000